

Research on the Translation and Dissemination Strategies of China's Poverty Alleviation Discourse: A Digital-Data Approach

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Junchao WANG¹; Chengcheng LI²

1. *Journal Department of GDUFS, Guangdong University of Foreign Studies, E-mail: 201510091@oamail.gdufs.edu.cn*
2. *School of Interpreting & Translation Studies, Guangdong University of Foreign Studies*

Abstract: Since 1949, China has continuously advanced poverty alleviation efforts. General Secretary Xi Jinping announced that China has completed the goals of poverty eradication in the new era as scheduled, achieving remarkable achievements that have attracted worldwide attention. This not only represents a great achievement of human civilization but also is crucial for China's foreign communication and the construction of its international image. In the current era of profound changes, constructing an external discourse system for poverty alleviation is of great significance in breaking Western discourse hegemony. Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party, theories and practices of poverty alleviation have continued to innovate, with the media playing a key role. However, there are still cognitive limitations and misunderstandings among overseas audiences regarding China's poverty alleviation efforts. In view of this, this paper constructs a database of poverty alleviation discourse written by Xi Jinping from the perspectives of international communication and foreign translation, and adopts the "Digital-data" approach. The aim is to provide a digital and intelligent pathway for China's external promotion of poverty alleviation discourse, thereby contributing to global poverty reduction as well as enhancing China's cultural soft power and international discourse power.

Keywords: China's poverty alleviation discourse, international communication, translation strategies, discourse database, Digital-data Theory

1. Introduction

Since the founding of P.R.C., the country has consistently carried out poverty alleviation and eradication efforts. General Secretary Xi Jinping pointed out that after eight years of persistent efforts, China has achieved the poverty alleviation goals of the new era as scheduled. Under the current standards, all rural impoverished populations have been lifted out of poverty, all impoverished counties have removed their poverty labels, absolute poverty and regional overall poverty have been eliminated, and nearly 100 million people have escaped poverty, securing a major victory that has drawn worldwide admiration. China's poverty alleviation is not only a monumental achievement in the history of human civilization but also a key element in China's international communication and the construction of its global image. Amid unprecedented changes in a century, building an international discourse system for China's poverty alleviation has become a crucial breakthrough in deconstructing the Western discourse hegemony of the "China threat theory", holding significant practical and theoretical implications (Hu, 2022). Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, China's poverty alleviation efforts have entered the phase of targeted poverty eradication, with continuous advancements in theoretical and practical innovations. This highlights the pivotal role of poverty alleviation in the decisive battle to build a moderately prosperous society in all respects and signals a transformation in poverty research and intervention models (Huang & Yuan, 2018).

The media has played a vital role in poverty alleviation, and delivering effective poverty alleviation reporting is an essential requirement for enhancing international discourse power (Zhang & Zhou, 2018). The coverage by mainstream local media across the country has profound significance for the progress of poverty alleviation. Analyzing their journalistic practices, discourse characteristics, and problems provides guiding insights for optimizing all poverty alleviation reporting (Jing, 2019). China's remarkable achievements in poverty alleviation have attracted global attention, yet overseas audiences still harbor numerous cognitive limitations and misunderstandings about China's poverty alleviation story (Luo & Zhou, 2020). Therefore, from the perspective of international communication and translation, this study constructs a self-built database of Xi Jinping's discourse on China's poverty alleviation, employs "digital-data" approach (Wang, 2024; Wang & Li, 2024), and thereby proposes a digital-intelligent pathway for the international promotion of China's poverty alleviation discourse. This not only offers a Chinese solution to global poverty reduction but also contributes to enhancing China's cultural soft power and international discourse influence.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Domestic Literature Review

Since the theme of “poverty alleviation” first appeared in Chinese academic research in 1985, the construction and development of China’s poverty alleviation discourse system have undergone four decades of refinement and accumulation, forming a multidimensional, cross-disciplinary research and dissemination framework. According to existing statistics, there have been 29,046 related research outputs domestically, showing a year-by-year growth trend (see Figure 1). This system not only encompasses multiple dimensions such as national poverty alleviation narratives, political discourse, documentaries, short films, films and television productions, literary works, news reports, ideological courses, academic research, and international topics, but also constitutes a vital component of China’s governance philosophy, exerting profound influence on poverty reduction efforts both within China and globally.

Figure 1. Trends in Academic Research on China’s Poverty Alleviation Discourse (1985-2024)

We will now provide a brief review from multiple dimensions, including theoretical research on China’s poverty alleviation, studies on national poverty reduction topics or narratives of poverty-alleviated nations, literary works on poverty alleviation themes, analyses of films and documentaries, examinations of domestic and international news reports, as well as research on curriculum-based ideological education and international relations related to poverty alleviation.

(1) Research on the Ontology of Poverty Alleviation Theory

In the ontological research of poverty alleviation theories, scholars have explored the theoretical foundations and practical pathways of China’s poverty eradication from various perspectives. For instance, Hu (2022) examined the construction, components, and approaches of China’s poverty alleviation discourse system for international audiences. Liu and Jiang (2021) focused on governance in daily life, proposing a theoretical paradigm and practical pathway for intervening in the poverty trap faced by households that have escaped poverty. Similarly, Zhang (2007) investigated the historical trajectory of China’s poverty alleviation and development efforts from 1949 to 2005. While these studies provide theoretical support for understanding the underlying logic of China’s poverty alleviation policies, research on how to effectively communicate these theories to the international community from a translation and communication perspective remains insufficient.

(2) Research on national poverty alleviation topics, political documents, or narratives of poverty-alleviated countries

At the national narrative level of poverty alleviation, Xi (2021) emphasized that “poverty alleviation is not the end goal” and proposed a series of poverty alleviation strategies (see our established database for details). Wang (2021) explored the perceptions and implications of African ambassadors in China regarding China’s poverty alleviation achievements. These studies analyze China’s poverty alleviation efforts from political and policy perspectives, but from the viewpoint of translation and communication studies, research on how to enhance international understanding and recognition of China’s poverty alleviation policies through external communication translation strategies remains relatively scarce.

(3) Literary Works on Poverty Alleviation Themes

The literary community has actively engaged in creating novels, poems, and other works centered on poverty alleviation, including “Chronicles of Bailizhou: A Firsthand Account of Poverty Eradication” by Zhu Chaomin, “Pipa Village” by Wen Yanxia, “The Nation’s Warmth: My Field Surveys from 2019 to 2020” by Jiang Wei, “Eighteen Stories from Shibadong Village” by Li Di, and “The Lofty Yuangu Dui” by Qin Ling. Zhao (2024) analyzed the literary portrayal of poverty alleviation in Liang Xiaosheng’s “Pastoral Ode”, while Yue (2023) explored the characterization and literary origins in novels on poverty alleviation themes. These studies reflect the social impact of poverty alleviation from a literary perspective, but research on how to convey China’s poverty alleviation stories through translated literary works and international publicity remains insufficient.

(4) Analysis of Documentaries and Short Films

In recent years, poverty alleviation has become a prominent theme in documentaries, short videos, and other audiovisual works. Examples include “Eradicating Poverty”, “Our Poverty Alleviation Stories in 2020”, “Monument: Xinjiang’s Poverty Alleviation Records”, and “Farewell to Poverty”, produced under the guidance of the Central Propaganda Department and China Media Group. “China’s War on Poverty”, a collaborative effort by the State Council’s Poverty Alleviation Office, CGTN, the Kuhn Foundation, and PBS Southern California, provides a comprehensive overview of China’s “targeted poverty alleviation and eradication” strategy. These works vividly document and showcase China’s remarkable journey and achievements in poverty alleviation through diverse perspectives and narrative techniques. In this regard, Wu and Zhang (2024) examined the representation of China’s national image in the new era through poverty alleviation documentaries, while Zhao (2023) analyzed the visual rhetorical strategies of “telling China’s stories well” using the short film “A Poverty Alleviation Story in a Cup of Coffee”. These studies highlight the significance of audiovisual works in shaping and disseminating national image, but further exploration is needed on how to enhance their international influence through translation and cross-cultural communication strategies.

(5) Analysis of Relevant News Reports from China and Abroad

In the analysis of Chinese and foreign news reports, Huang and Zhang (2022) conducted a critical discourse analysis of poverty alleviation and eradication coverage in mainstream Western and Chinese media based on corpus data. Yu (2024) examined the use of reporting verbs in news reports on “targeted poverty alleviation”. These studies provide comparative perspectives on media coverage, but from the standpoint of translation and communication studies, research on how to optimize such reports to enhance international communication effectiveness remains insufficiently explored.

(6) Research on Poverty Alleviation in Ideological and Political Education or International Relations

In the context of ideological and political education and international relations research, Teng (2022) explored the integration of the spirit of poverty alleviation into ideological and political courses in higher education, while Lu and Chen (2022) analyzed poverty alleviation from the perspective of global governance. These studies offer new insights into poverty alleviation education and international cooperation. However, from the perspective of translation and communication studies, there is significant room for development in research on how to disseminate China’s poverty alleviation experience through educational and international cooperation platforms.

2.2 Review of International Research Trends

Research on “poverty” is quite extensive internationally. According to incomplete statistics, it covers numerous languages and regions, including English (85,362 articles), Korean (167 articles), Spanish (148 articles), French (118 articles), Turkish (108 articles), Japanese (93 articles), Portuguese (78 articles), Russian (68 articles), Polish (51 articles), German (50 articles), Arabic (42 articles), Croatian (33 articles), Afrikaans (29 articles), and more. One of the earliest monographs on the subject is Krauth’s “Poverty”, published in 1858. Between 1800 and 1950, a total of 1,068 monographs discussed the ontology of “poverty” and its relationships with waste, resources, development, wealth disparity, education, population, war, regions, stability, and other factors. Among these early studies, some focused on the theme of “poverty alleviation”, such as classic works like “The Destruction of Poverty” (Robinson, 1898), “Poverty and Dependency” (Gillin, 1926), “The Abolition of Poverty” (Hollander, 1914), and “Prohibiting Poverty” (Martin, 1933).

One of the earlier studies on China is “Population, Poverty And Prosperity: China’s Environmental Woes” (Russell, 1989), which analyzed the relationship between population, poverty, development, and the environment. Related works were published later, such as “Poverty Issues and Policies in China” (Tong, 1991), “China: From Afforestation to Poverty Alleviation and Natural Forest Management” (Rozelle, Huang, Husain & Zazueta, 2000), “Roads Improvement for Poverty Alleviation in China” (Hajj & Pendakur, 2000), and “China: Overcoming Rural Poverty” (World Bank, 2001).

Since international institutions raised the issue of “poverty alleviation in China” in the early 21st century, global research on this topic has become more focused. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) China Office (2003) analyzed the relationship between poverty alleviation in China and microfinance. International studies have continued to adopt multidimensional analytical perspectives, such as the links between poverty alleviation and the environment (Groom et al., 2010), poverty and water resources (Cohen & Sullivan, 2010), poverty alleviation and property rights (Webster, Wu, Zhang & Sarkar, 2016), poverty alleviation and social security (Hammond, 2019), and poverty alleviation and health (Muttaqin, 2024). On the other hand, much of the research employs quantitative empirical methods. For instance, Duclos, Araar & Giles (2010) measured and estimated chronic and transient poverty in China; Cohen & Sullivan (2010) developed a multidimensional assessment tool to evaluate the relationship between water resources and poverty in rural China; Sullivan (2011) further analyzed the impact of risk, time, and poverty on China’s forest tenure reform; Meng (2013) used regression

discontinuity methods to assess China’s poverty alleviation programs; Ward (2016) empirically analyzed transient poverty, poverty dynamics, and vulnerability in rural China; Westmore (2018) and Gustafsson & Sai (2023) both employed comparative data analysis to examine China’s poverty reduction efforts. Additionally, research on China’s poverty alleviation campaign has expanded into multidimensional studies, such as Bakre & Dorasamy (2023) exploring the lessons of China’s poverty alleviation for rural development in South Africa; Liu, Du, and Liu (2024) conducting a multimodal analysis of posters related to China’s poverty alleviation efforts; and Muttaqin (2024) examining the health impacts of China’s poverty alleviation campaign on rural populations from a medical perspective, among others.

Overall, existing research in China has covered theoretical discussions on poverty alleviation, analyses of films and television works, comparisons of news reports, studies on national issues, literary representations, as well as ideological education in curricula and international relations. However, most studies focus on domestic perspectives and practices. From the perspective of translation and communication studies, how to effectively convey China’s successful experiences and stories of poverty alleviation to the international community, and how to shape a positive image of China on the global stage, remains a research gap that urgently needs to be addressed. Future research could pay more attention to cross-cultural communication strategies, techniques for international publicity translation, and communication mechanisms in international cooperation, to enhance the global dissemination and influence of China’s poverty alleviation discourse.

3. Linguistic Features of Chinese Economic Discourse and Translation Strategies

By collecting Chinese and English corpus on the theme of poverty alleviation from *Xi Jinping: The Governance of China* (Volumes I to IV), we have established a poverty alleviation discourse corpus, which includes 10 key articles. Using this thematic data as the corpus, the following will provide a digital-data analysis of China’s poverty alleviation discourse.

3.1 Keywords in Poverty Alleviation Discourse

In the era of big data, with the help of powerful text analysis tools, we can conduct comprehensive and systematic visual analysis of China’s poverty alleviation discourse database. The total number of characters in the Chinese and English poverty alleviation-themed articles from Volumes I to IV are 14,587 and 20,530, respectively. The keywords are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. High-Frequency Content Words in Chinese and English Databases

Chinese Corpus				English Corpus			
r	Rank	Word	Freq.	r	Rank	Word	Freq.
1		脱贫	250	1		poverty	3092
2		贫困	229	2		areas	769
3		扶贫	158	3		alleviation	754
4		攻坚	144	4		impoverished	595
5		发展	124	5		should	571
6		地区	110	6		must	448
7		我们	96	7		development	444
8		全面	81	8		rural	407
9		群众	79	9		people	362
10		问题	68	10		poor	350
11		坚持	67	11		party	348
12		工作	66	12		cpc	338
13		社会	63	13		targeted	274
14		实现	62	14		fight	261
15		党	61	15		central	223
16		年	59	16		villages	203
17		人口	54	17		have	200
18		人民	54	18		elimination	199
19		解决	49	19		prosperous	198
20		经济	48	20		moderately	197
21		保障	46	21		ensure	175
22		资金	46	22		measures	175
23		农村	44	23		china	171

The narrative of poverty alleviation and eradication is an overlay of political and economic issues such as rural development, a moderately prosperous society, rural revitalization, and the community with a shared future for mankind. It is a long-term news agenda aligned with the national social security system and social assistance (Yang, 2023). At its core, however, the discourse on poverty eradication revolves around efforts to combat poverty. Metaphor is one of the commonly used rhetorical devices in China’s poverty alleviation discourse (Zeng, 2022), as it vividly conveys the essence of poverty relief policies and development philosophies, making them more persuasive and engaging. By analyzing databases, it becomes evident that metaphors are extensively employed in China’s poverty alleviation discourse to explain specific policy measures, including “poverty eradication” (a campaign), “policies” (flood irrigation, targeted treatment, precision drip irrigation, targeted therapy, taking root, staggered advancement, flipping pancakes), “standards” (weights and measures, appetite), “work style construction” (tightening the institutional cage), “cadres” (those who act get positions, those who endure hardship gain favor), “outstanding issues” (leaving no dead ends, filling the gaps), and “railways” (accelerators).

Figure 2. Keywords in China’s Poverty Alleviation Discourse: A Visual Representation of Poverty Eradication

In the Chinese database spanning Volumes 1 to 4, the term “poverty alleviation” appears 250 times, while “poverty” occurs 430 times in the English database. Across the four volumes, the frequencies are 9, 148, 115, and 158 times respectively, showing a relatively even distribution in poverty alleviation discourse articles. Through further analysis of its contextual collocations, we can identify several common structures:

- **Noun phrases:** poverty alleviation, poverty elimination, the fight against poverty, the battle against poverty, wars on poverty, poverty-stricken areas, poverty alleviation and development, etc.;
- **Preposition + poverty:** against poverty, out of poverty, etc.;
- **Verb + poverty:** break away from ..., leap from ..., emerge from ..., escape from ..., rise from ..., etc.;

FilePath	FileTokens	Freq	NormFreq	Dispersion	Plot
四卷六第四篇 英语.docx	6729	158	23480.458	0.923	
二卷二第三篇 英语.docx	1424	65	45646.067	0.899	
二卷二第四篇 英语.docx	2422	73	30140.380	0.884	
三卷五第二篇 英语.docx	1967	57	28978.139	0.869	
三卷五第三篇 英语.docx	1869	51	27287.319	0.844	
一卷七第一篇 英语.docx	518	9	17374.517	0.692	
三卷五第四篇 英语.docx	913	6	6571.742	0.556	
二卷二第二篇 英语.docx	3214	8	2489.110	0.130	
三卷五第一篇 英语.docx	286	1	3496.503	0.000	
二卷二第一篇 英语.docx	1188	2	1683.502	0.000	

Figure 3. The Concordance Plot for the Keyword “poverty alleviation”

(2) The Conceptual Metaphor Network of Poverty Alleviation

Cognitive linguist Lakoff’s conceptual metaphor theory posits that metaphor is not merely a rhetorical device but a reflection of the conceptual system in human language. At its core, metaphor involves using a concrete concept (the source domain) as a reference to understand and interpret another, more abstract or less directly graspable concept (the target domain). This process constitutes a mapping from one cognitive domain to another, embodying human thought patterns. China’s discourse on poverty alleviation is rich in metaphorical expressions, employing vivid and figurative language to describe and explain specific policy measures for poverty eradication. By closely examining the 430 contexts in which “poverty” appears in the database, we can derive the conceptual metaphor set for the “poverty alleviation” discourse: \sum AGAINST POVERTY IS X = {AGAINST POVERTY IS MAKING GOLD. AGAINST POVERTY IS RUNNING. AGAINST POVERTY IS BATTLE. AGAINST POVERTY IS VOYAGE. AGAINST POVERTY IS TAKING WING. ...}

Figure 4. The Conceptual Metaphor Net

(2) Metaphorical Expressions of Poverty Alleviation

In China’s discourse on poverty alleviation, there exist both conceptual metaphors shared by Chinese and English, as well as unique mapping relationships specific to the Chinese context.

Source text 1: 只要有信心，黄土变成金。(Volume 1)

Source text 1 Romanized: Zhǐ yào yǒu xìn xīn, huáng tǔ biàn chéng jīn.

Target Text 1: With confidence, even barren clay can be turned into gold.

AI Deepseek: With strong faith, even the barren soil can turn into gold.

AIPE: With strong faith, even the barren soil can be turned into gold.

The original text primarily discusses helping people in revolutionary base areas and impoverished regions overcome poverty and achieve prosperity. Both versions effectively capture the metaphor of poverty alleviation. Since humans are the agents of poverty alleviation, the subject of this sentence is implied. In English, passive voice is often used in such cases, making the official translation's voice more appropriate. However, the AI version conveys a more resolute tone, which can also reflect the difficulty of poverty alleviation in reverse.

Source text 2: 脱贫攻坚战的冲锋号已经吹响。(Volume 2)

Source text 2 Romanized: Tuō pín gōng jiǎn zhàn de chōng fēng hào yǐ jīng chuī xiǎng.

Target Text 2: We have sounded a clarion call in the battle against poverty.

AI Deepseek: The clarion call for the battle against poverty has been sounded.

AIPE: The clarion call for the battle against poverty has been sounded.

The use of the metaphor “poverty alleviation is a battle” here helps readers better understand the importance the Party and the state attach to this matter. Both the official and AI translations effectively preserve the original metaphorical treatment, with the only difference being that the official version uses the pronoun “we” as the subject. English articles typically avoid first-person pronouns to maintain objectivity, so the AI version aligns better with English expression norms and requires no modifications.

Source text 3: 我在福建宁德工作时就讲“弱鸟先飞”，就是说贫困地区、贫困群众首先要有“飞”的意识和“先飞”的行动。(Volume 2)

Source text 3 Romanized: Wǒ zài Fú jiàn Níng dé gōng zuò shí jiù jiǎng “ruò niǎo xiān fēi”, jiù shì shuō pín kùn dì qū、pín kùn qún zhòng shǒu xiān yào yǒu “fēi” de yì shí hé “xiān fēi” de xíng dòng.

Target Text 3: When I worked in Ningde, Fujian Province, I told the locals a folktale titled *A Weak Bird Takes Flight Early*. My intention was to explain to them that the area and the people should do two things – first, “take wing” and then “leave the nest”.

AI Deepseek: When I was working in Ningde, Fujian, I often mentioned that “the weaker bird must fly first,” which means that impoverished areas and people must first have the consciousness to “take flight” and the initiative to “fly ahead.”

AIPE: When I worked in Ningde, Fujian, I told the locals a folktale titled *A Weak Bird Takes Flight Early*, and the purpose was to explain to them that *in order to escape poverty*, the area and the people must first “take flight” and then “leave the nest”.

The original sentence is based on the story of “The slow (or clumsy) bird must fly early,” using “fly” as a metaphor for the requirements of poverty alleviation. It suggests that while the state provides external support, the “wings” are their own. Since impoverished individuals lack innate advantages, they must rely on acquired efforts to prosper. The official translation uses “take wing,” which originally means “to take off,” here metaphorically representing “to begin development.” Similarly, “leave the nest” carries a comparable meaning, effectively replicating the metaphorical sense of the original. In contrast, the AI version is confusing and unclear. Moreover, the speaker is emphasizing the principle of “the slow bird must fly early” in the present context, not recalling a past “emphasis,” so the past continuous tense is unnecessary. Therefore, the AI’s translation has been revised accordingly.

Source text 4: 不搞大水漫灌，不搞“手榴弹炸跳蚤”，因村因户因人施策，对症下药、精准滴灌、靶向治疗，扶贫扶到点上扶到根上。(Volume 3)

Source text 4 Romanized: Bù gǎo dà shuǐ màn guàn, bù gǎo “shǒu liú dàn zhà tiào zāo”, yīn cūn yīn hù yīn rén shī cè, duì zhèng xià yào, jīng zhǔn dī guàn, bǎ xiàng zhì liáo, fú pín fú dào diǎn shàng fú dào gēn shàng.

Target Text 4: We do not spray preferential policies indiscriminately or “kill fleas with a hand-grenade”. Instead, we adopt targeted measures for different villages, households and individuals according to their specific conditions, so that we can address the root causes of poverty.

AI Deepseek: We will not employ a one-size-fits-all approach, nor will we use a sledgehammer to crack a nut. Instead, we will tailor our measures to the specific conditions of each village, household, and individual, ensuring targeted and precise interventions. Our poverty alleviation efforts will be focused on the root causes and key areas, delivering assistance where it is most needed and effective.

AIPE: We do not spray preferential policies indiscriminately or use a sledgehammer to crack a nut. Instead, we tailor our measures to the specific conditions of each village, household, and individual, ensuring targeted and precise interventions. In a word, assistance is delivered where it is most needed and effective.

The paragraph containing this sentence summarizes poverty alleviation practices, so the future tense is unnecessary. It can be observed that both versions retain the metaphor only in the first half, with the official translation handling the expression “flood irrigation” more vividly. Additionally, the official version is more concise than the AI’s. Based on this, the AI’s translation was edited to produce the post-edited version.

Source text 5: 对脱贫县要扶上马送一程，设立过渡期，保持主要帮扶政策总体稳定。(Volume 4)

Source text 5 Romanized: Dui tuō pín xiàn yào fú shàng mǎ sòng yī chéng, shè lì guò dù qī, bǎo chí zhǔ yào bang fú zhèng cè zǒng tǐ wěn dìng.

Target Text 5: To buttress counties that have emerged from poverty, we will institute a transition period during which the main poverty alleviation support policies will generally remain in place.

AI Deepseek: For counties that have emerged from poverty, we will provide continued support to ensure a smooth transition. We will establish a transitional period during which the main assistance policies will remain generally stable, helping them to firmly establish their footing and move forward steadily.

AIPE: For counties that have emerged from poverty, we will give them a leg up. We will establish a transitional period during which the main assistance policies will remain generally stable, helping them to firmly establish their footing and move forward steadily.

The phrase “扶上马送一程” in the original text means that elders should provide comprehensive assistance during the growth of younger generations. Both translation versions have somewhat lost the original metaphorical meaning. Compared to the official translation, the AI version is slightly repetitive but clearer in conveying the meaning at the end. Through conversations with AI and consulting electronic dictionaries, it was found that “扶上马送一程” can be expressed in English with the relatively close phrase “give someone a leg up”, which means helping someone get started or providing initial support. This phrase also aligns with the literal meaning of mounting a horse in reality, making it suitable for further revisions of the translation.

4. Conclusion

As a key component of China’s political discourse, the discourse on poverty alleviation is critically linked to the effectiveness of its international communication and the quality of its foreign translation. These factors are deeply intertwined with the construction of China’s international discourse power and the shaping of its global image. This study innovatively integrates theories from translation studies, communication studies, and political science, employing a digital-data approach facilitated by digital intelligence. Through systematic collection of Chinese and English corpus data centered on poverty alleviation from *Xi Jinping: The Governance of China* (Volumes 1–4), the research successfully assembles a specialized corpus of poverty alleviation discourse and accurately extracts key thematic keywords.

Poverty alleviation discourse not only embodies distinctive literary charm and profound philosophical insights but also vividly encapsulates China’s valuable economic development experiences. Due to space limitations, this study primarily focuses on the metaphorical expressions within the corpus. Additionally, by leveraging AI technologies, it conducts in-depth comparative analyses between translations produced by professional human translators and AI-generated translations. This endeavor aims to explore how, in the era of artificial intelligence, technological advancements can be harnessed to provide more high-quality and efficient support for the international dissemination of China’s poverty alleviation discourse.

Finally, with ongoing technological progress and continuous scholarly inquiry, it is anticipated that the research scope will expand further to explore the deeper connotations and strategic dissemination of poverty alleviation discourse. Such efforts will help to promote the grand achievements and valuable experiences of China’s poverty alleviation campaign on the international stage more broadly and profoundly, thereby contributing stronger Chinese wisdom and strength to the global poverty reduction initiatives.

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